

reference to a recent assignment of the vibrational bands in tris-(acetylacetonato) cobalt(III) based on a normal coordinate analysis^{1,2}. The $\nu\text{C}=\text{C}$ band observed in the range 1580-1540 cm^{-1} , while $\nu\text{C}=\text{O}$ band observed at about 1530-1510 cm^{-1} range. The bands observed in the range 3350-2950 cm^{-1} for the complexes (I) to (IV) may be assigned as due to $\nu\text{N}-\text{H}$ vibrations. Ionic ClO_4^- absorbs at 1180-1100 cm^{-1} in the complex (II). Antisymmetric and symmetric stretching vibrations of COO^- observed at 1605 cm^{-1} and 1410 cm^{-1} respectively in the complex (IV).

Experimental details are the same as described previously¹⁻⁴.

Acknowledgement

We are thankful to Professor N. N. Ghosh of Calcutta University, Department of Chemistry for allowing us to use the Gouy balance and to Dr. S. N. Poddar of Indian Association for the Cultivation of Science, Calcutta-32, for spectral measurements. Thanks are also due to U. G. C. (New Delhi) for financial help.

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Reduction of Br(V) with Mn(II), Ce(III), [Fe(phen)₃]²⁺ and [Ru(dipy)₃]²⁺

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Manuscript received 27 April 1978, revised 5 January 1979,
accepted 6 June 1979

MANGANESE(II), cerium(III), tris 1, 10-phenanthroline iron(II) and 2,2'-dipyridyl ruthenium(II) are known¹⁻³ to act as catalysts in Belousov's oscillating reaction (metal ion catalysed reaction between acid bromate and citric acid or its substitute) in which metal ion species oscillate between their reduced and oxidised form and Br(V) is reduced by these reduced form of the metal ions. Since there is no sufficient and systematic report on the reduction of Br(V) with these reductants, in continuation of our studies^{4,5} on Belousov's reaction, we are reporting here our findings on the reduction of Br(V) with Mn(II), Ce(III), [Fe(phen)₃]²⁺ and [Ru(dipy)₃]²⁺ in aqueous 3*N* H₂SO₄ acidic medium.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of extra purity. 1, 10-phenanthroline iron(II) and 2,2'-dipyridyl ruthenium(II) complexes were prepared following the methods reported earlier^{6,7}.

Potentiometric titrations were done by a modified method^{8,9}. 10 ml of M/60 solution of KBrO₃ was delivered to a number of reaction vessels and then M/10 solution of the reductants were delivered to each reaction vessel in increasing order and potentiometric readings were recorded after the storage of the reaction mixture at different time intervals during which reaction mixture attains equilibrium. All experiments were carried out at room temperature (25°).

Results and Discussion

In case of reduction of Br(V) with manganese(II), sharp inflexions were observed at 1.8, 3.4 and 6.7 ml corresponding to 1st, 2nd and 4th electron reduction stages of Br(V) which is suggestive of the formation of BrO₂, HBrO₂ and HBr respectively at those stages. A very sharp inflexion at 6.7 ml corresponds to 4th electron reduction stage of Br(V), i.e., formation of hypobromous acid which was confirmed and titrated with arsenite. The

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colour of the solution corresponding to inflexion at 6.7 ml was cherry red which was due to the formation of trivalent manganese in the solution and was confirmed by spectrophotometric measurements which showed maximum absorption at 500 nm.

The stoichiometry observed was

TABLE I—POTENTIOMETRIC DATA OF REDUCTION OF Br(V) BY Mn(II)

(Cell : 10 ml BrO_3^- , Reductant M/10 manganous sulphate)

Medium 3N H_2SO_4 , Temp. $25^\circ \pm 0.05^\circ$

Storage time	Position of inflexion in ml	Nature of inflexion
1.5 hr	1.8	Very sharp
	6.7	
3 hrs	1.8	Sharp
	3.4	
	6.7	
24 hrs	1.8	Very sharp
	3.4	
	6.8	

The observation is in good agreement with the work of Thompson¹⁰.

In case of reduction of Br(V) with Ce(III) only one inflexion was obtained at 8.5 ml after 1 hr storage of the reaction mixture at room temperature which corresponds to 5th electron reduction stage of Br(V). Even after 24 and 48 hrs storage of the reaction mixture the only inflexion obtained at 8.5 ml which is suggestive of the formation of bromine, also supports the 5th electron reduction stage of Br(V).

Tris (1, 10-phenanthroline) iron(II) and tris (2,2'-dipyridyl) ruthenium(II) act as reductants. The formal reduction potential³ of $\text{Fe(phen)}_3^{2+} - \text{Fe(phen)}_3^{3+}$ couple is 1.1 v and for $\text{Ru(dipy)}_3^{2+} - \text{Ru(dipy)}_3^{3+}$ is 1.25 v. Reaction of Br(V) with $[\text{Fe(phen)}_3]^{2+}$ and $[\text{Ru(dipy)}_3]^{2+}$ showed consumption of 10.2 and 10.4 ml of the reductants respectively which suggests 6th electron reduction stage of Br(V) in both the cases. Presence of Br^- at those stages were confirmed.

Acknowledgement

Authors acknowledge thankfulness to Council of Scientific and Industrial Research, New Delhi, for the award of a Post-doctoral Fellowship to one of them (C.M.S).

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Base Adducts of Bis-(Chloro Acetyl-Acetonato)-Zinc(II) with Nitrogen Donors

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Manuscript received 2 November 1977, revised 26 March 1979,
accepted 6 June 1979

METAL chelates of beta-diketones and related compounds which involve keto-enol tautomerism have invoked lot of interest in recent years. Attempts have been made for the adduct formation of metal beta-diketonates with heterocyclic amines and a number of pentacoordinated adducts of zinc(II) and copper(II) beta-diketonates with nitrogen donors have been reported¹⁻⁷. Stability of acetyl acetonates has been partly explained on the basis of benzenoid resonance⁸ and reactions characteristic of aromatic systems have been carried out⁹⁻¹¹ on metal acetyl acetonates to provide further evidence regarding aromaticity. It was thought worthwhile to study the adduct formations of gamma-substituted beta-diketonates and as a part of this investigation adducts of bis-(nitroacetyl-acetonato) copper(II) have been reported^{12,13}. This communication reports four pentacoordinated adducts of bis-(chloroacetylacetonato)-zinc(II) with quinoline, isoquinoline, gamma-picoline and quinaldine.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. Bis-(chloroacetylacetonato) zinc(II) was prepared by reacting a methanolic solution of the metal chelate with dry chlorine gas and by cooling the reaction mixture in an ice bath. The white compound separated was filtered, washed with methanol, followed by ether and dried in vacuum. Analysis of the compound indicated the composi-